

Selection of Primary Sources in AGIS

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approved by:
reference: GAIA-C3-TN-LU-LL-093-01
issue: 1
revision: 0
date: 2011-12-12
status: Issued

Abstract

This note describes how the selection of primary sources for the core astrometric solution (AGIS) should be made, initially and in subsequent solutions.

Document History

Issue	Revision	Date	Author	Comment
1	0	2011-12-12	LL	Issued without any change from first draft.
D	0	2011-05-23	LL	Creation and 1st draft

1 Why do we need primary sources?

The astrometric core solution for Gaia (also known as AGIS) will use a subset of the $\sim 10^9$ sources observed by Gaia for a robust least-squares estimation of their astrometric parameters simultaneously with a large number of ‘nuisance parameters’ representing the attitude, geometric calibration, and global effects. The subset of sources used in AGIS is referred to as the *primary sources*. The off-line analysis of other sources, including solar system objects and ‘secondary’ sources (typically double and multiple stars) use the nuisance parameters from this solution, but do not contribute to their determination. The selection of primary sources is a dynamical process, and will be different in successive cycles or even in the course of a single AGIS solution. The terms *relegation* and *promotion* are used for the processes by which the status of a source is changed from primary to secondary, respectively from secondary to primary.

The purpose of this note is to outline procedures for the selection of primary sources at different stages of the processing, as well as criteria for the relegation and promotion of sources within AGIS. The current design of AGIS aims at using up to 10^8 primary sources. However, since the initial solutions could be run with much fewer sources, while the final run could conceivably use many more, the total number (N) of primary sources will be a main input parameter for the selection process. This is also motivated by the trivial circumstance that the time needed to run AGIS is mainly a function of N .

Before going into the more technical description of the selection/relegation/promotion processes it may be useful to review why the concept of primary sources is needed in the first place.

A pre-requisite for accepting a source as primary is that its location (as determined in IDT or IDU) can be accurately modelled in AGIS by means of the time-varying proper direction calculated for a well-defined and fixed set of (astrometric) parameters. For a majority of the sources, the ‘standard’ five-parameter astrometric model¹ (Lindegren et al., 2011) is known to be sufficient even for the very high precision of the Gaia measurements. This standard model has been adopted for the astrometric solution, and consequently only sources that behave according to this model can be accepted as primary sources. Well-behaved quasars are also adequately described by the same model: the circumstance that their parallaxes are effectively zero and that their proper motions should behave in a certain way does not invalidate the model, and quasars can therefore be included among the primary sources.

Compliance with the standard five-parameter model is thus a necessary condition for a source being accepted as a primary. Furthermore, if a compliant source is accepted as a primary, it cannot harm the solution in the sense that the nuisance parameters become less well determined or biased. This follows from a well-known property of linear least-squares estimation, namely that

¹The standard model includes a sixth parameter μ_r , depending on the radial velocity of the source. However, for the present discussion we consider the radial velocity to be known (with default value equal to zero, if not measured), so that there are never more than five free parameters per source.

the estimate is unbiased if the model is correct and the noise unbiased. With centred noise, bias can only be introduced through modelling errors. Statistically speaking, including one more compliant primary source in the AGIS solution can then only make the nuisance parameters more accurate.

Although model compliance is a necessary condition, it is not sufficient to conclude that the source should be selected as a primary. There are several reasons why a source might not be selected even if it fits the standard model perfectly. Two main considerations, to be discussed below, are (1) that, for purely practical reasons, we usually want to limit the total number of primary sources, and (2) that the question what constitutes a good fit is not a trivial one.

With a limited total number of primary sources (N), it is nearly always necessary to reject many otherwise acceptable sources. This must be done in a clever way to optimize the estimation of the nuisance parameters while taking into account the specific requirements of the attitude determination and geometric calibration, e.g., concerning gated observations. The convergence speed of AGIS, if not the final accuracy, could also be improved by making the weight distribution on the sky more uniform, i.e., by rejecting sources in high-weight areas.

In the presence of observation noise it is never possible to say for sure that the standard model is correct. (On the other hand, it is often possible to conclude, with high confidence, that the model is wrong.) If the standard model fits the data with good residuals, we can at most conclude that there is no evidence *in the astrometric data* against the model. However, other data might give reason to doubt the validity of the model for some sources, for example based on their photometric or spectroscopic variability. Such sources may be rejected as primaries even if the standard model *seems* to fit the astrometric data adequately, simply because modelisation errors, and hence biases in the estimated parameters, can be suspected at some level even if they are not visible in the data.

Model compliance will be judged based on statistical criteria whose sensitivity to model deviations is a strong function of the precision and number of elementary observations of the source. Very minute modelling errors could become visible for the brightest sources, while large deviations may pass unnoticed for faint sources. However, we should remember that also the attitude and instrument models are subject to errors. For example, significant residuals for the bright sources might be the result of poor instrument or attitude modelling, rather than being intrinsic to the sources. Ideally, this should not lead to the sources being rejected as primaries; on the contrary, they will be important for improving the the instrument and attitude modelling. If, on the other hand, the large residuals are caused by source modelling errors, it could indeed be desirable to relegate these sources. How can the different cases be distinguished?

The adopted procedure for assigning weights to the observations and for identifying outliers (Lindgren, LL-083) provides a partial answer to this. It is designed to be robust against isolated outliers as well as source and attitude modelling errors, but may also provide indication about instrument modelling errors. Effectively, the statistical weights of individual observations are

adjusted to reduce the overall harm to the solution. For a particular source (i) the badness of the fit to the standard model is indicated by the so-called excess source noise $\epsilon_i \geq 0$ determined as part of the source update process. A large ϵ_i is an indication that the source is perhaps not a good primary, but there could be other explanations as well. For example, if most stars with gated observations are found to have a large excess noise, then a more probable cause is a problem with the instrument model for gated observations rather than with the sources themselves. Conversely, if only a fraction of the bright sources have a large excess noise, it is more probably caused by their binarity, and the affected sources should then not be used as primaries. In either case, the statistical weights are reduced depending on the size of ϵ_i in relation to the formal (photon-statistical) standard errors, as described in Lindegren (LL-083). Although this reduces the influence of the modelling errors on the solution, it would be better to improve the modelling (if the attitude or instrument models are the culprits) or relegate the source (if that is the problem). The robustness should rather be seen as a safeguard against the unavoidable borderline cases.

2 Gated sources

In this section we introduce the idea of a ‘gated source’. This may seem strange, as it is the individual observations that are gated (or not), not the sources. Indeed, many bright sources will sometimes be observed in gated mode, sometimes not, depending on the on-board magnitude estimation. Additionally, any sources could obtain gated observations simply because they happen to be observed at nearly the same time as some bright source.

The actual gating scheme to be used is not yet decided, but a reasonable first guess is given in de Bruijne (JDB-036). Not all 12 gates will be used, but only (say) $g = 4, 8, 9, 10, 11,$ and 12 . We use $g = 13$ to identify ungated observations.

We use the following definition: a source is classified as ‘gated’ if at least half of its observations (up until the current point in time) were gated. Gated sources are assigned the index g corresponding to the most common gate among its gated observations; ungated sources are assigned $g = 13$. Thus, every source has a unique index g . As part of the AGIS pre-processing, statistics are collected about the number of sources for different g . In order to guarantee that the gates can be properly calibrated, a sufficient number of primary sources must be selected for each value of g .

3 How many primary sources are needed?

The *minimum* number of sources required for AGIS is driven by the calibration needs of having a sufficient number of sources per calibration unit at different magnitudes, in particular for the geometric calibration of gated observations, and by the attitude needs of having a sufficient

number of sources with AC observations in every knot interval.

Let us consider first the requirements for the geometric small-scale calibration of the CCDs, where a resolution in the AC coordinate of one or a few pixel columns is required. The angular extent of a single CCD in the across-scan direction is about 0.1° . It scans the celestial sphere at a rate of 1° min^{-1} and therefore covers about 2000 deg^2 per week, if both fields of view are counted. Since there are 1966 pixel columns across the CCD, we have the convenient rule of thumb that each pixel column covers 1 deg^2 per week. Thus, if the average density of suitable primary sources is $D \text{ deg}^{-2}$ and we require a minimum of M observations of such sources per pixel column for its calibration, then the minimum time needed is M/D weeks. For example, with $N = 10^8$ primary sources we have $D = 2400 \text{ deg}^{-2}$, and it is then reasonable that the small-scale calibration can be made, at a resolution of one or a few pixels, in a matter of weeks. However, for the gated observations of bright sources ($G \lesssim 12 \text{ mag}$), the available numbers are much smaller and it will be necessary to sacrifice resolution in time, number of pixels, or both in order to have a sufficient number of observations per calibration cell. For example, the gate used for the brightest sources will perhaps mainly be used for $G \simeq 5.7$ to 8.8 ; the *total* number of such stars is about 130 000 (from the Tycho-2 Catalogue) or $D \simeq 3 \text{ deg}^{-2}$, of which only a fraction may be suitable as primary sources. Thus, even over the whole five-year mission there will only be a few hundred observations per pixel column. From these considerations it is clear that as many as possible of the bright stars (or more specifically the gated sources) should be selected as primary sources, no matter where they happen to be on the sky.

Consider next the requirements for the attitude determination. The minimum reasonable knot interval is of the same order as the transit time over a CCD, or about 5 s. Since we require both along-scan and across-scan measurements, and the latter are normally only provided by the SM and AF1 observations, we assume conservatively one observation in each coordinate per field-of-view transit. There are seven CCDs across the width of the field of view; the area scanned is therefore 1000 deg^2 per day in each field of view, or 0.06 deg^2 per 5 s interval. If we require, say, 100 transits per knot interval for a reliable attitude determination, then the minimum density of primary sources is $D = 1700 \text{ deg}^{-2}$, or some 70 million sources in total. To achieve this density in the galactic pole regions requires that stars as faint as $G \simeq 19$ are included among the primary sources. Thus it is clear that the design aim of $N \simeq 10^8$ primary sources is quite reasonable, and that these will have to include both very bright and very faint stars, as well as many quasars down to $G = 20$ for the extragalactic link.

Apart from these minimum requirements, the quality of the solution (in terms of the accuracy of the nuisance parameters) will only improve, the more (good) primary sources are included. Stated in the negative sense, the solution quality cannot improve by removing good-quality primary sources. From this viewpoint one should clearly aim to include as many primary sources as possible, at least in the final solution.

On the other hand, it is of course possible to run AGIS with much fewer primary sources by disabling short-term small-scale calibrations and using longer knot intervals for the attitude.

FIGURE 1: Distribution of relative astrometric weight per half-magnitude bin (see text for further explanation.)

This will increase modelling errors, which is acceptable for initial runs where the input data have not yet been properly calibrated.

At any stage of the Gaia data processing, the number of primary sources actually used will be a compromise between accuracy (favouring as many as possible) and convenience or practical constraints (favouring as few as possible). Figure 1 illustrates this point. It shows, for each half-magnitude bin, the total astrometric weight potentially available on the whole sky, based on star counts in Drimmel et al. (GAIA-ML-022) and the predicted AL location-estimation performance in the astrometric field according to de Bruijne (JDB-053). It is assumed that a constant fraction of the stars in each magnitude bin are potentially useful as primary stars, so that the total weight is proportional to $N(G)/\sigma_l^2(G)$, where $N(G)$ is the number of stars in the bin and $\sigma_l(G)$ the corresponding standard error of the AL location estimate. For stars brighter than $G \simeq 13$, the use of gates means that σ_l is roughly independent of magnitude, and the total weight per magnitude bin increases in proportion to the number of stars. For fainter stars, the increased N only partly compensates for the increased standard error per observation, resulting in the downward trend for $G > 13$. The interval $G = 6$ – 13 thus contains 28% of the total weight, but only 1% of the stars; $G = 13$ – 16 contains 50% of the weight and 7% of the stars, while $G = 16$ – 20 contains 22% of the weight and 92% of the stars.

4 Quantities available for the selection of primary sources

A source has to pass several tests, derived from different processes, in order to qualify as a primary source. As outlined above, the most important test is derived from the AGIS solution itself, and is based on how well the standard five-parameter astrometric model fits the data, as quantified by the excess source noise ϵ_i .

The ‘relegation factor’ U has been introduced as an attribute to every source that is processed through the AGIS primary or secondary source update. The relegation factor is a floating-point number ranging from 1 to infinity. $U \simeq 1$ implies that the source is perfect for use in the astrometric solution, while successively larger values indicate less suitable sources. The relegation factor may incorporate the results of several different tests, and therefore provides a continuous variable for use in the selection process. A primary source is relegated into a secondary one if U exceeds a predefined value, which may happen for example in the course of the AGIS iterations, or from one solution to the next. On the other hand, a secondary source may be promoted to a primary if its U value decreases below the set threshold.

The source updating estimates the excess source noise ϵ_i as described in Lindegren (LL-083). In the absence of other information about the source, the relegation factor is then computed using

$$U_i = \sqrt{1 + [\epsilon_i/e(G_i)]^2}, \quad (1)$$

where $e(G)$ is a normalization factor depending on the (mean) magnitude G of the source. The function $e(G)$ determines the balance between absolute and relative contributions to the modelling error budget. With the choice $e(G) \simeq \sigma_l(G)$ (the formal AL observational standard error for a source of magnitude G), U_i approximates the RMS normalized residual of the source. Selecting sources based on this U_i tends to discriminate against bright stars where modelling errors may dominate over photon-noise errors. On the other hand, choosing $e(G) = \text{constant}$ means that only sources with the smallest ϵ_i are accepted; this may remove too many of the faint sources, where ϵ_i is significant but still small in comparison with σ_l . A reasonable compromise between these two extreme cases must be found.

Apart from the relegation factor, which indicates whether a source is at all suitable as a primary source, the general principle should be to maximize the total weight of the primary sources. The weight of a source i is defined as

$$W_i = \frac{1}{n_i} \sum_{l \in i} \frac{w_l}{\sigma_l^2 + \epsilon_i^2}, \quad (2)$$

where the average is taken over the $n_i = \sum_{l \in i} 1$ accepted AL observations of the source. $0 \leq w_l \leq 1$ is the downweighting factor determined for every observation as part of the source updating (it is < 1 only for identified outliers), and σ_l is the formal standard error obtained from the image parameter determination in IDT or IDU.

The relegation factor U_i and weight per source W_i are the main quantities available for the selection/relegation/promotion process, and are therefore needed for every potential primary source. These sources must therefore be processed through the source update (as part of the AGIS pre-processing), after which its initial status as primary/secondary can be decided.

In the later cycles of processing, when significant information have been collected about the photometric, spectroscopic and astrophysical properties of the sources, additional quantities will be defined that can be used as selection criteria. Examples of such information could be:

- LSF fitting: A bad fit to the LSF in the IDT or IDU could indicate duplicity or some other source structure. A goodness-of-fit measure is calculated for every elementary observation, and a relevant indicator for a given source is the median goodness-of-fit from all its elementary observations.
- Resolved and astrometric binaries: The downstream object analysis will reveal some sources as resolved binaries or multiple stars, while others that are unresolved or only partially resolved will have photocentres with detectably non-linear orbital motion. These should in general not be selected as primary sources.
- Photometric variability: If an object is variable, and at the same time a binary (and the *a priori* probability of the latter is of course quite high), the photocentre may shift back and forth between the components in relation to their (variable) flux ratio. This kind of objects (VIM = variability-induced movers) was identified already in the Hipparcos Catalogue (Wielen, 1996), and although useful astrometric information can sometimes be extracted by combining the photometric and astrometric observations, such sources with *significant* photocentric amplitudes are clearly unsuitable as primary stars.
- Spectroscopic variability: This usually means a spectroscopic binary, and depending on the period and other characteristics, the photocentre of the system may or may not have a significant astrometric amplitude.
- Other potentially problematic sources: It is possible that some extreme objects (extreme colours, large angular diameter, ...) are unsuitable as primary sources.

We have not yet defined criteria for how these indicators should be used to define selection criteria. The general principle should be that sources are rejected as primaries based on the *expected* size of the astrometric effect (say, ξ_i), in relation to the photonstatistical error. Assuming that ξ_i can somehow be estimated, a logical way to include it in the selection process would be to compute a combined excess noise $(\epsilon_i^2 + \xi_i^2)^{1/2}$ to be used in Eqs. (1)–(2) instead of ϵ_i .

5 Selection procedure

5.1 General algorithm

The algorithm described in this section is designed to ensure sufficient sky coverage (i.e., a certain minimum number density everywhere) for the attitude determination, while respecting the pre-defined maximum total number N and maximizing the total weight. Concerning the gated sources, there may be the additional requirements of at least a specified number (N_g) of primary sources per gate index g .

In addition to N and $\{N_g\}$, two parameters must be specified: the minimum density D_{\min} (deg^{-2}) required for the attitude determination (with $N \geq (129600/\pi)D_{\min}$), and a tentative maximum acceptable relegation factor U_{\max} . Then:

1. Using a coarse-grained pixelization of the celestial sphere (see below), select in each pixel the N_p sources with the largest W_i that satisfy $U_i \leq U_{\max}$. Here $N_p = \lceil A_p D_{\min} \rceil$ is the minimum number of primary sources per pixel that will ensure D_{\min} , if A_p is the pixel area in deg^2 .
2. For each gate index $g < 13$, count the actual number of primary sources already selected; if it is less than N_g add sources with $U_i \leq U_{\max}$ based on W_i .
3. If the total number after Step 1 and 2 is less than N , add sources with $U_i \leq U_{\max}$, based on W_i , irrespective of their positions on the sky. If the total number exceeds N_{tot} , reduce U_{\max} and repeat the process.

If the required number cannot be reached in a particular pixel or magnitude bin, then it is necessary to increase U_{\max} locally for that pixel or bin.

For the pixelization in Step 1 in principle any tessellation scheme could be used, but for statistical operations HEALPix (Górski et al., 2005) has some advantages (O'Mullane et al., 2001). The pixel size is determined by the choice of HEALPix parameter $NSIDE$ and is important as it predicts the level of homogeneity over the sphere. A pixel area of about 1/3 of the field of view might be close to optimal, and is achieved with $NSIDE = 128$ yielding 196608 pixels.

5.2 Initial selection

For the very first run with real data some selection must be made using the initial star catalogue. However, the observations of all sources will be fed through the source update process (as part of the AGIS pre-processing) during which U_i and W_i will be computed, so the above procedure is valid also in this case. The pre-processing uses (at least partially) the attitude from FL, and a

potential problem could be that the attitude might have a very uneven quality. For example, if part of the attitude comes from a preceding AGIS run, while the latest data have a much worse attitude, it is possible that a large fraction of the new data is rejected as outliers. This can be prevented by assigning reasonable values for the excess attitude noise along the whole time line.

5.3 Relegation and promotion of sources

In any AGIS run, the first few iterations will use the simple iteration scheme, which allows a dynamical adjustment of weights (in the form of the excess source noise and excess attitude noise) and downweighting factors between successive iterations. After these values have settled, it may be advantageous to run the secondary-source process (essentially a source update for all non-primary sources), make a new selection of primaries and start a new AGIS, including a re-determination of the weights. The new selection means that some primaries are relegated to secondary status, and some previous secondaries are promoted to primaries. However, there seems to be no need to define separate algorithms for the relegation and promotion procedures; they can be handled by the general algorithm described in Sect. 5.1.

6 References

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